

Report for Survey Experiment in Esplugas

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Overview:

On the 9th of June 2022, tests for the ONA robot (a prototype last-mile delivery robot) were conducted in the municipality of Esplugas de Llobregat. As such the robot was traversing public spaces in the view of pedestrians. The researchers for the project found this an ideal moment to conduct surveys to these pedestrians in order to gain insight into the public opinion of integrating a last-mile delivery robot with the public space. I was given the task and opportunity to approach pedestrians and ask them to fill out these surveys.

Contents of the Survey:

The online version of the survey that was used for this study is linked below:

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSfskX8mi3Nr3e1rYXcnCzBwZBnAqhCta3eDpt25jHD7vl-Zqw/viewform?usp=sf_link

This survey states the following:

“The main objective of this survey is to analyse the integration of transport robots in the urban public space for last-mile goods distribution, both for homes and businesses”

As such, the questions have to do with the comfort levels that people have with ONA and any other future robot present in their public space. Various questions over different scenarios of the robots context are asked in order to gain insight into where people may have notions that robots belong. This includes asking questions about the build of the robot, the type of environment it is in, whether or not it should be fully autonomous or accompanied by a human escort, etc.

Also in the survey, two robots are shown with pictures in order for the people taking the survey to be able to contextualize the robot. In many of the cases, people took the survey as they watched the robot ONA conduct its experiments in the public space they were a part of.

The following are some of the pictures shown in the survey:

Helena Robot: urban mobile robot that can interact with people and perform parcel distribution tasks

ADD robot: robot-vehicle that can perform its movement autonomously using a 3D Lidar system and laser technology

Execution of the Surveys:

The method that was used to survey people was as follows. The researchers and I would go onto the plaza and ask passers-by's to take the survey. They were given the option to take it on paper or to use a qr code to get a link to the survey on their smartphone.

Generally, the demographics of the people who took the survey in person were retirees. This would make sense as the surveys were conducted in the public space on a Thursday morning which is generally when people with jobs are at the workplace. Also it is important to note that Esplugas is more suburban than the main city of Barcelona that it is around. This resulted in less foot traffic in the plaza compared to that that would occur in a major city; although, it was still sufficient for our purposes. Also, the area seemed more residential and family-oriented which

provides a reason why it was difficult to find young professionals and adults to survey.

The following are pictures that were taken that day:

Left:
Observing the
ONA robot being
prepared for the
experiments

Right:
Preparing the
surveys with the
researchers

Thoughts and Observations:

The following are the observations that I made while conducting the surveys and observing pedestrians respond to the presence of an autonomous robot in the public space.

It can be said that generally, people have a positive response to having last-mile delivery robots integrated into the public space. Here might be a few reasons why:

1. The reserved, methodical, and predictable movements that the robot made during its experiments in the public raised no worry for the danger that it could have possibly invoked. No one in the public space feared for their safety as the experiments were conducted which is a merit that can be attributed to the developers of the robot.
2. The increasing presence of digital and robotic technologies in everyday life. As time goes on, people are beginning to see technology being integrated into their everyday lives. Whether it is ordering food from a tablet, having access to the internet with a smartphone, or riding in autonomous vehicles, technology assisting humans is becoming more commonplace and welcome.
3. People may consider it more convenient and safe to get a package delivered by a robot. The idea is that it would reduce shipping costs and make the delivery of everyday items to any place easier than it already is. This allows for expanded business opportunities.

Despite this, people still held some reservations about the integration of a last-mile robot in the public space. The following are trends that I noticed:

1. Retirees were more likely to have more negative feelings towards the robot. They were concerned about it interfering with their daily lives and about the negative impacts it can have by changing the way that life in the public space now is.
2. One of the biggest concerns was over job loss in the delivery industry. Counter arguments were made by the researchers that today's delivery jobs will be replaced with HRI jobs where humans monitor and maintain the robots. While this is true, the only viable way that delivery robots will ever be fully implemented is if they are cheaper than human labor. Therefore, the money that delivery companies have that is given to human laborers will be allocated towards robots and less would end up being given to the human workers as a result. Therefore with less capital being allocated towards human workers, there will be job loss. The extent and magnitude of this job loss is up for debate, but it is a valid concern nonetheless.
3. Safety was the concern of a few people when they realized that these robots would traverse the same streets as the ones that children and the elderly use. This is a valid point, yet the developers are working on the safety features as one of the top priorities of the project. If the robots were ever to integrate with public space, it is safe to assume that they would have to pass extensive safety tests and would have some form of human monitoring.

Overall, the experience of giving the surveys was a good insight into seeing the public opinion of last-mile delivery robots. It was interesting to see the patterns of the different points and concerns that people brought up.